

Bootstrapping from S_n to S_{n+1}

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Previous articles [1] – [5] have detailed the elements of S_4 , S_5 , and S_6 , obtained in various ways, often after extensive computational effort. Along the way graphical displays eased the burden of just staring at numbers.

But what goes on is actually simpler.

The shortest group S_2 is composed of the two tags 12 and 21. Treated as decimal integers, these two can serve as sources for S_3 ; but how?

Plus-up each digit by 1, then append a 1 at the beginning, to get 123 and 132 respectively. This clearly amounts to adding 111 to 12 and 21 treated as decimal integers.

Now 123 and 132 will source S_3 via circulant evolution; the output tags are obviously

123, 231, 312 and 132, 321, 213

Thus a 'plus-up, append, circulate' (or PAC) bootstrapping got S_3 from S_2 .

Next, given the S_3 sextet, the source set for S_4 via 'plus-up and append' is

1234, 1342, 1423, 1243, 1432, and 1324.

Each tag is distinct, and generates three more 'circulates'; thus a total of $4 \cdot 6 = 24 = 4!$ unique tags, exactly the size of S_4 . Of course, to obtain its specific elements the PAC process needs to be executed; the immediate results are tabled below, where sources are in white.

1234	1342	1423	1243	1432	1324
4123	2134	3142	3124	2143	4132
3412	4213	2314	4312	3214	2413
2341	3421	4231	2431	4321	3241

Recall that to recover the matrix (mx) corresponding to each vector tag (tx), do in OCTAVE

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for k=1:4,mx(k,tx(k))=1;end
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Each foursome in the boxes above is unique, and has corresponding matrices add to the matrix of all 1's; thus the 'fill-the-gap' feature. Moreover, the integer sum of every tag in S_4 is 10, or more generally $n(n + 1)/2$, the sum of consecutive integers up to and including n.

For completeness, the PAC process will be used to generate S_5 from the 24 elements of S_4 . First, the 'plus-up and append' operations yield the sources as

12345	12354	12435	12453	12534	12543	13245	13254	13425	13452	13524	13542
14235	14253	14325	14352	14523	14532	15234	15243	15324	15342	15423	15432

The 'circshift' command (or the permutation matrix $P_{ij} = \delta_{i,j+1}$) 'circulates' to complete S_5 ; the sources are highlighted in yellow.

12345	12354	12435	12453	12534	12543	13245	13254	13425	13452	13524	13542
51234	41235	51243	31245	41253	31254	51324	41325	51342	21345	41352	21354
45123	54123	35124	53124	34125	43125	45132	54132	25134	52134	24135	42135
34512	35412	43512	45312	53412	54312	24513	25413	42513	45213	52413	54213
23451	23541	24351	24531	25341	25431	32451	32541	34251	34521	35241	35421
14235	14253	14325	14352	14523	14532	15234	15243	15324	15342	15423	15432
51423	31425	51432	21435	31452	21453	41523	31524	41532	21534	31542	21543
35142	53142	25143	52143	23145	32145	34152	43152	24153	42153	23154	32154
23514	25314	32514	35214	52314	53214	23415	24315	32415	34215	42315	43215
42351	42531	43251	43521	45231	45321	52341	52431	53241	53421	54231	54321

Finally, the source set for S_6 obtained from S_5 in the same fashion matched perfectly the set previously obtained more laboriously in [3]; thus circulant evolution would complete S_6 as well.

More generally, consider first the following facts about S_n for any $n \geq 2$.

- 1) The group has $n!$ elements
- 2) Each individual element is a string of the form $k_1k_2k_3\dots k_n$, where the k_j 's are all distinct integers ranging in value from 1 to n
- 3) The individual digit sum of any element is the sum of all integers from 1 to n , namely $n(n+1)/2$
- 4) Every element can generate $(n-1)$ additional 'circulates' for a total of n

To bootstrap to S_{n+1} the 'plus-up and append' operation adds the $(n+1)$ -long string 1111...1 to the digit string $k_1k_2k_3\dots k_n$ to get the $(n+1)$ -long string $1(k_1+1)(k_2+1)(k_3+1)\dots(k_n+1)$; this forms the 'source' set. Circulant evolution then generates $(n+1)$ unique elements from each single result; since there are $n!$ total elements in S_n , the grand total of $(n+1)n! = (n+1)!$ indeed fits the size of S_{n+1} .

To complete the argument, note that the digit sum for each new element after 'plus-up and append' is

$$1 + (k_1+1) + (k_2+1) + (k_3+1) + \dots + (k_n+1) = (n+1) + n(n+1)/2 = (n+1)(1+n/2) = (n+1)(n+2)/2$$

exactly the sum of all integers from 1 to $(n+1)$; thus the PAC bootstrap works.

References

- [1] A. Cusmariu, 'Spawning S_4 from Kronecker products', [10.5281/zenodo.10452480](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10452480)
- [2] A. Cusmariu, 'S4 once over easy', [10.5281/zenodo.10613871](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10613871)
- [3] A. Cusmariu, 'S5: piece of cake, almost', [10.5281/zenodo.10630734](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10630734)
- [4] A. Cusmariu, 'S6: The whole enchilada and more', [10.5281/zenodo.10654847](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10654847)
- [5] A. Cusmariu, 'S6 again: Circulant evolution at work', [10.5281/zenodo.10687840](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10687840)